

1 **EFFECTIVENESS OF SPATIAL TRAINING IN ELEMENTARY AND**
2 **SECONDARY SCHOOL: EVERYONE LEARNS**

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25 **RESUMEN**

26

27 El procesamiento visoespacial es clave para lograr, entre otros, un rendimiento óptimo
28 en actividades académicas. En el ámbito de la cognición espacial se ha encontrado que la
29 práctica con tareas espaciales puede reducir la brecha de género en este tipo de razonamiento.
30 Sin embargo, no siempre un aumento de las puntuaciones espaciales llega a compensar las
31 diferencias que existen entre participantes con mayores y menores habilidades espaciales. De
32 acuerdo con estudios previos sobre diferencias individuales y maleabilidad en cognición
33 espacial, se necesitan estudios comparables en niños, niñas y adolescentes utilizando el
34 mismo método de evaluación y entrenamiento. En este trabajo se analiza, en 39 estudiantes
35 de Educación Primaria (estudio 1: 17 niños y 22 niñas) y en 21 de Educación Secundaria
36 (estudio 2: 11 chicos y 10 chicas), el perfil de evolución a través de las diferentes sesiones de
37 un entrenamiento en rotación mental (RM), así como el grado de mejora producido en
38 función de su capacidad espacial de partida, analizando el factor género. En ambos grupos, se
39 aplicó un entrenamiento espacial (Programa de Entrenamiento en Rotación Mental) durante
40 tres sesiones consecutivas con una duración promedio de 35 minutos por sesión. Para ambos
41 grupos de edad, los participantes con bajo nivel espacial se beneficiaron en una proporción
42 similar que aquellos participantes con más recursos espaciales. Este resultado se replicó para
43 ambos sexos. Esta investigación servirá como punto de partida para promover e implementar
44 entrenamientos adaptativos y personalizados, y así poder ayudar a los que menos capacidades
45 espaciales tienen. Este tipo de intervenciones ganarían en eficacia y podrían maximizar el
46 potencial educativo en los grupos más desfavorecidos.

47 PALABRAS CLAVE

48 Rotación Mental; Entrenamiento; Diferencias de género, Ganancias de ejecución;
49 Estrategias Educativas

50

51 ABSTRACT

52 Visuospatial processing is key to achieve optimal performance in academic activities,
53 among others. In the field of spatial cognition, it has been found that practice with spatial
54 tasks can reduce the gender gap in this type of reasoning. However, an increase in spatial
55 scores does not always compensate the differences that exist between participants with
56 greater and lesser spatial abilities. According to previous studies on individual differences
57 and malleability in spatial cognition, comparable studies are needed in children and
58 adolescents using the same evaluation and training method. In this work, the evolution
59 profiles across three sessions of a mental rotation (MR) training of 39 students from Primary
60 Education (study 1: 17 boys and 22 girls) and 21 from Secondary Education (study 2: 11 boys
61 and 10 girls) were analyzed, as well as the degree of improvement obtained based on their
62 initial spatial performance, analyzing the gender factor. In both groups, a spatial intervention
63 (Mental Rotation Training Program) was applied during three consecutive sessions with an
64 average duration of 35 minutes per session. For both age groups, participants with a low
65 spatial level benefited at a similar rate as those participants with more spatial resources. This
66 result was replicated for both genders. This research will serve as a starting point to promote
67 and implement adaptive and personalized training, and thus be able to help those with less
68 spatial skills. These types of interventions would become more effective and could maximize
69 educational potential among the most disadvantaged groups.

70

71 KEYWORDS

72 Mental rotation; Training; Gender Differences; Achievement gains; Educational
73 Strategies

74

75 INTRODUCTION

76 Spatial content is usually present in academic areas related to science, technology,
77 engineering, or mathematics, so that visuospatial skills can predict success in these
78 disciplines to a certain extent (Humphreys, Lubinski, & Yao, 1993). Some meta-analyses
79 have shown that visuospatial training can improve the performance of this skill (e.g., Uttal et
80 al., 2013). Researchers linked to the area of education have incorporated spatial interventions
81 into the classroom so that these skills can “permeate” into academic disciplines such as
82 mathematics (e.g., Hawes et al., 2017; Lowrie et al., 2017).

83 Some interventions to improve cognitive functions have analyzed the gains produced
84 after training based on initial abilities, finding greater benefits in those individuals with lower
85 levels of working memory (Karbach et al., 2015) and reading performance in schoolchildren
86 (García -Madruga et al., 2013), or in divided attention in adults (Baniqued et al., 2014).

87 Interventions focused on spatial cognition, more specifically on Mental Rotation (MR),
88 have shown differences in performance in favor of males (e.g., Linn & Petersen, 1985).
89 However, practice with spatial tasks can minimize the gender gap by equalizing this ability
90 across both genders after training in schoolchildren (De Lisi & Wolford, 2002; Ehrlich et al.,
91 2006), adolescents (Neubauer et al., 2010) and university students (Cherney et al., 2014).

92 Fernández-Méndez et al. (2020) analyzed the differential gains according to starting
93 spatial level among 3- and 5-year-old preschoolers. Participants with a poorer initial ability
94 showed a greater increase in their MR ability after training only the 5-year-old group. Studies
95 have also been carried out with adolescents on the effects of training according to individual
96 starting differences, finding disparate results. David (2012) studied 14-year-old students who
97 played video games related to MR, Visualization (Vz) and spatial relationships and found that
98 students with low initial scores significantly improved their MR performance compared to
99 those with better initial skills after playing video games. However, the author did not find any
100 gender effect, nor any interaction between baseline and gender. The findings of Bergner and
101 Neubauer (2011) among 15-year-old students with high abilities in visuospatial aptitude
102 suggested that the group of girls with a lower spatial performance improved more in the
103 accuracy of the task after training, although not in Response Times (RT). In the context of
104 cognitive deficits, Wiedenbauer and Jansen-Osmann (2007) found that boys and girls aged
105 between 8 and 14 years diagnosed with spina bifida benefited considerably from training,
106 improving their RT and their success ratio in a computerized MR task, equaling the
107 performance of healthy children.

108 Individual differences in MR have also been analyzed in adults, with training through
109 the *Tetris* video game, finding disparate results. While some authors have seen that
110 inexperienced players benefit as much as expert players in this video game (Sims & Mayer,
111 2002), others have found that those with worse initial skills yielded higher increases, equaling
112 in the last sessions those with high spatial skills (Terlecki et al., 2008). Another study by
113 Contreras et al. (2018) also found that university students with lower initial skills in Vz
114 improved significantly more compared to their peers with better initial skills.

115 In summary, although most studies point towards a more pronounced improvement
116 after training in those participants who initially exhibit lower initial spatial ability, there are
117 studies that have found that participants with better or worse level benefit equally from
118 spatial training. On the other hand, an influential meta-analysis, which has confirmed the
119 malleability of spatial skills, highlights the lack of research at various ages with a similar

120 training method in order to obtain comparable results (see Uttal et al., 2013, for a review).
121 Given the scarce literature on studies that analyze individual performance with MR tasks, we
122 aim to search for more evidence using for the first time an analogous method in evaluation
123 and training across two educational stages that are crucial, Primary (childhood) and
124 Secondary (adolescence). Encouraging spatial reasoning in Primary Education could be key
125 for boys and girls to reach an optimal level of visuospatial reasoning in later stages, such as
126 adolescence, in which students must determine which academic path they wish to follow, this
127 being crucial for their future career. Therefore, educational interventions of a spatial nature
128 that take place before or during adolescence could be relevant, especially when the presence
129 of women is scarce in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics) careers,
130 where spatial reasoning seems to play an important role.

131

132 **Objectives and hypotheses**

133 The objective of the two studies (Primary and Secondary students) of the present work
134 was to analyze the progress over three training sessions in an MR task, as well as the
135 performance as a function of a high or low spatial ability, measured in the criterion test
136 applied, and verifying that the two groups were comparable in general intelligence.
137 Participants with a lower baseline ability in the spatial test were expected to achieve a similar
138 level after training as those starting from a higher level. The performance was evaluated
139 through measures of success (correct answers, CA) ratio and response time (RT) for each of
140 the sessions of the task. The two studies carried out with 39 primary school students and 21
141 secondary school students are shown below, belonging only to the groups that underwent MR
142 training (EG, hereinafter). The results related to the pre-test and post-test differences, as well
143 as the improvements exhibited in spatial ability after training in the experimental and control
144 groups can be seen in Rodán et al. (2019) for the primary school group, and in Rodán et al.
145 (2016) for the high school group.

146

147 **STUDY 1**

148 **Method**

149 *Participants*

150 In this study, 39 students ($M = 7.68$ years, $SD = 0.66$; 17 boys and 22 girls) in second
151 year of Primary Education from two public schools (“CEIP Escuelas Aguirre” and “CEIP
152 Leopoldo Alas”), located in a central area of Madrid, with a medium-high sociocultural level,

153 took part. These were students belonging to the EG of a previous study, where performance
154 was compared between a trained group (EG) and another untrained control group (CG,
155 hereinafter) (Rodán et al., 2019).

156 *Materials*

157 *Raven's Progressive Matrices (SPM version; Raven, Court, & Raven, 1996)*

158 This test evaluates general intelligence from the age of 6. The test consists of 60
159 exercises divided into 5 series with 12 elements each, and it is executed without a time limit,
160 although the average duration of the test is 40-90 minutes. Each slide has 6 or 8 answer
161 options, with only one correct answer. The maximum possible score is 60 points. The split-
162 half reliability is .90, while the test-retest ranges between .83 and .90 (Seisdedos, 1995).

163

164 *EFAI-1 spatial aptitude test "E"*

165 It is a subtest of the Factorial Assessment of Intellectual Aptitudes battery (Santamaría
166 et al., 2005), validated for 7- to 10-year-olds. It evaluates the ability to mentally imagine
167 movements and transformations of an object in space. It is considered an approximation to
168 the visual processing factor, "Gv" –Lohman, 1996– (p. 17). It has 30 exercises with four
169 response options each, in which the participant must decide which of the four response
170 stimuli fits as a puzzle into a reference target by rotating them. The duration of the test is six
171 minutes, and the maximum score is 30 points. The reliability of this test is .86 (see an
172 example of an item in Rodán et al., 2019).

173

174 *Mental Rotation Training Program (PERM-Programa de Entrenamiento de Rotación Mental,* 175 *in Spanish)*

176 The PERM is composed of 480 tests, and each one consists of a white mold on a gray
177 box (reference target) located on the left side of the screen, and two two-dimensional figures
178 located on the right, numbered as "1" and "2", shaped identical to the mold. The PERM's task
179 is to imagine transformations and rotations, deciding which of the two stimuli "1" or "2"
180 matches the mold if it is rotated. Only one of the two stimuli fits inside the mold (Figure 1).
181 The intra- and inter-session difficulty of the task was manipulated according to the
182 characteristics of the stimuli - close and concrete figures or abstract figures - and the number
183 of difficult trials increased as sessions progressed. During the execution of PERM, the
184 participant had to answer each of the trials, so that the program recorded 450 trials of the 480
185 that were presented (the first 10 trials of each session were used as familiarization with the

186 task). In each session, the correct answers (hits) and response times for each trial were
 187 computed. The *E-Prime version 1.2* computer software (Psychology Software Tools, 2002)
 188 was used for the programming, presentation of stimuli and data collection of the PERM task
 189 (for additional information on PERM, see Rodán et al., 2019).

199 *Figure 1.* Example of a trial used in PERM in Study 1

200

201 *Procedure*

202 The tests were administered on consecutive days, with one session per day, for a total
 203 period of five days (one day for the pre-test, three days of training and one day for the post-
 204 test).

205 On the first day (pre-test phase), the Raven's Progressive Matrices were administered
 206 collectively first and then the EFAI-1, with a five-minute break between the two. It was
 207 carried out in the students' usual classroom with four examiners, and the tables were
 208 organized individually.

209 For the next three days, each participant performed the training task (PERM)
 210 individually on a computer in three consecutive sessions. After the 10 pre-training trials, the
 211 150 trials of the task itself were carried out, divided into two blocks of 75 presentations, with
 212 a 5-minute break between both blocks. The experimenters stressed the importance of
 213 precision throughout the training, insisting that they could take all the time necessary to
 214 ensure a correct answer. All trials had to be answered in a forced way as the possibility of
 215 blank answers was not contemplated. The number of trials per session presented in PERM
 216 was 5850 (150 trials x 39 participants). -After eliminating certain trials due to premature
 217 answers or excess time consumed, a total of 5723 (97.8%), 5656 (96.7%) and 5655 (96.7%)
 218 trials were analyzed in Sessions S1, S2 and S3, respectively. After eliminating these trials, the

219 minimum performance times were 311.4 sec. (5.19 min.), 335.4 sec. (5.59 min.) and 223.2
220 sec. (3.72 min.). Whereas, the maximum performance time was 1176 sec. (19.6 min.), 1416
221 sec. (23.6 min.) and 1290 sec. (21.5 min.) for S1, S2 and S3, respectively.

222 Finally, on the last day (post-test phase), the Raven Progressive Matrices and EFAI-1
223 tests were administered under the same conditions as in the pre-test phase.

224 The legal guardians of the children signed an informed consent, according to the
225 Declaration of Helsinki, complying with the data protection regulations and the approval of
226 the Ethics Committee of the UNED.

227

228 *Data Analyses*

229 To confirm that the groups were comparable in intelligence according to the level of
230 spatial ability (high: “↑ SA”; low: “↓ SA”), and in both genders, a one-factor ANOVA was
231 performed for the measure obtained in the Raven in the pretest phase. To examine the
232 evolution profile through the different training sessions as a function of SA level and gender,
233 a mixed $2 \times 2 \times 2$ repeated measures ANOVA was carried out with “SA level” (low, high)
234 and “Gender” (boys, girls) as inter-subjects factors, and with repeated measures “Session”
235 (Session 1, Session 2 and Session 3) as intra-subjects factor. This analysis was applied to the
236 dependent variables "proportion of correct answers" (number of correct answers/total trials in
237 each session) and "response time" (time between the presentation of the trial and the correct
238 answer), in the training phase.

239 Finally, to analyze the gains obtained in spatial ability (EFAI-E) as a function of SA
240 level and gender, a $2 \times 2 \times 2$ repeated measures ANOVA was carried out with “SA level”
241 (low, high) and “Gender” (boys, girls), as inter-subjects factors, and with “pre-post repeated
242 measures” (pre-test, post-test) as intra-subjects factor.

243 Statistical analyzes were performed with the *SPSS statistical software, version 24.0*
244 (IBM Corp., 2016) with a significance level of .05.

245

246 **Results**

247 *Preliminary Analyses*

248 Preliminary analyses showed that both groups (↓ SA and ↑ SA) did not differ in their
249 scores on the intelligence test of the pretest phase. No gender differences were found for the
250 entire group, nor for the interaction between group and gender factors.

251

252 *Performance during PERM and gains obtained in MR skill*

253 The level of SA (\downarrow SA and \uparrow SA) of the participants was determined according to the
 254 skills observed in the spatial test (EFAI-E) in the pretest phase, using the median as a cut-off
 255 point, which in this study was 9 points.

256 In the PERM performance analysis, all trials with RTs less than 500 ms (Wiedenbauer
 257 & Jansen-Osmann, 2007), and RTs greater than 60 seconds were excluded for all participants,
 258 so that 516 trials (2.94% of the total) were finally eliminated. The average RT (in seconds)
 259 for each participant was calculated only for the correct answers following the same procedure
 260 used in classical reference studies for the analysis of performance in Mental Rotation tasks
 261 (Shepard & Metzler, 1971; Voyer & Jansen, 2016).

262 Table 1 shows the descriptive analyses of the proportion of correct answers and of the
 263 RTs of the correct trials. The mixed ANOVA 2 (Gender) x 2 (SA level) for the proportion of
 264 correct answers revealed a main effect of the SA level in Session 1 [$F(1, 35) = 5.67, MSE =$
 265 $.073, p = .023, \eta^2_p = .14$], in Session 3 [$F(1, 35) = 4.251, MSE = .068, p = .047, \eta^2_p = .11$],
 266 and for the total of all sessions [$F(1, 35) = 4.19, MSE = .050, p = .048, \eta^2_p = .11$], so that
 267 participants with \uparrow SA obtained a higher proportion of correct answers in these three
 268 conditions: [CA-S1: \downarrow SA: $M = 0.78, \uparrow$ SA: $M = 0.87$, mean difference = 0.09, $p = .02$], [CA-
 269 S3: \downarrow SA: $M = 0.72, \uparrow$ SA: $M = 0.80$, mean difference = 0.08, $p = .04$], [CA-TOTAL: \downarrow SA: M
 270 $= 0.75, \uparrow$ SA: $M = 0.82$, mean difference = 0.07, $p = .04$]. No other main effects or
 271 interactions between factors were found. The repeated measures ANOVA 3 (Session) x 2
 272 (gender) x 2 (SA level) only showed a significant effect in the Session factor [$F(2, 70) =$
 273 $18.9, MSE = .056, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .35$]. The proportion of correct answers progressively
 274 decreased from S1 to S3, and the pairwise comparisons showed a higher proportion of correct
 275 answers in S1 compared to S2 and S3 [S1: $M = 0.83; S2: M = 0.76; S3: M = 0.76$; mean
 276 difference S1-S2 = 0.06, $p < .001$; mean difference S1-S3 = 0.07, $p < .001$]. No significant
 277 interactions between factors were found for this variable. The RT analysis only showed a
 278 significant interaction between the factors Gender x SA level for Session 2 [$F(1, 35) = 7.08,$
 279 $MSE = 11432, p = .01, \eta^2_p = .17$] and for the total of all sessions [$F(1, 35) = 4.53, MSE =$
 280 $4249, p = .040, \eta^2_p = .12$], which was explained by longer RTs in girls in the \uparrow SA group
 281 [RT- S2 (\uparrow SA): boys: $M = 4.2$ sec.; girls: $M = 6.0$ sec.; mean difference = 1.8 sec., $p < .01$],
 282 [RT-TOTAL (\uparrow SA): boys: $M = 4.4$ sec.; girls: $M = 5.6$ sec.; mean difference = 1.2 sec., $p =$
 283 $.01$]. A marginal effect of the Gender factor was also observed in Session 3 [$F(1, 35) = 4.05,$
 284 $MSE = 8997, p = .052, \eta^2_p = .10$], due to the shorter RTs in boys than in girls (boys: $M = 4.7$

285 sec.; girls: $M = 5.6$ sec.; mean difference = 0.9 sec., $p = .052$). No other main effects or
 286 interactions between factors were found. The repeated measures ANOVA 3 (Session) 2
 287 (Gender) x 2 (SA level) did not show any main effect or interactions between factors. Figure
 288 2 shows the performance through the different training sessions in Primary students.

289

290 Table 1

291 *Descriptive statistics (means and standard deviations) of the proportion of correct answers and RTs of correct trials*
 292 *(in seconds) for each session and for the total of the three sessions of PERM in Primary school students.*

293

Measures	Total (N = 39)			
	↓SA (n = 20)		↑SA (n = 19)	
	Boys (n = 9)	Girls (n = 11)	Boys (n = 8)	Girls (n = 11)
	M (SD)	M (SD)	M (SD)	M (SD)
CA-S1	0.78 (0.13)	0.79 (0.15)	0.86 (0.06)	0.88 (0.08)
CA -S2	0.71 (0.13)	0.77 (0.12)	0.76 (0.12)	0.82 (0.10)
CA -S3	0.69 (0.15)	0.74 (0.13)	0.79 (0.11)	0.81 (0.11)
CA-TOTAL	0.73 (0.13)	0.77 (0.13)	0.80 (0.09)	0.84 (0.09)
RT-S1	5.2 (1.3)	4.6 (1.1)	4.6 (0.6)	5.1 (0.9)
RT-S2	5.4 (0.8)	5.0 (1.3)	4.2 (0.8)	6.0 (1.8)
RT-S3	4.8 (1.5)	5.5 (2.0)	4.5 (0.7)	5.8 (1.2)
RT-TOTAL	5.2 (0.7)	5.0 (1.3)	4.4 (0.6)	5.6 (1.0)

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Figure 2. Proportion of correct answers (A) and response times of correct trials (B) for the interaction Sessions 1 to 3 x gender x level of spatial ability in Primary students

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Table 2 shows the descriptive analyses of the scores obtained in the EFAI-E for both genders and according to the spatial ability level. The repeated measures ANOVA 2 (pre-post) 2 (Gender) x 2 (SA level) for the dependent variable “EFAI-E”, only showed a main effect on the pre-post factor [$F(1, 35) = 79.1, MSE = 827, p < .001, \eta_p^2 = .69$], thus explaining a general gain in MR ability. No other significant interactions between factors were found.

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Tabla 2

Descriptive statistics (means and standard deviations) of the scores obtained in the EFAI-E for both genders of the group of Primary participants with low and high level of spatial ability.

↓SA (n = 20)			
EFAI-E (max. = 30)	Boys (n = 9)	Girls (n = 11)	TOTAL
	M (SD)	M (SD)	M (SD)
Pretest	6.33 (1.32)	6.73 (1.68)	6.55 (1.50)
Post-test	14.4 (5.13)	13.3 (4.59)	13.8 (4.74)
Increment	8.11 (4.70)	6.55 (4.80)	7.25 (4.70)
↑SA (n = 19)			
EFAI-E (max. = 30)	Boys (n = 8)	Girls (n = 11)	TOTAL
	M (SD)	M (SD)	M (SD)
Pretest	13.6 (3.82)	12.0 (3.13)	12.7 (3.43)
Post-test	20.6 (3.38)	16.6 (5.59)	18.3 (5.09)
Increment	7.00 (3.93)	4.64 (4.65)	5.63 (4.41)

313

314 Discussion

315 The objective of this study was to examine the individual differences in performance
316 across the different sessions of an MR training program, as well as the differential gains as a
317 function of the starting spatial level in schoolchildren in 2nd year of Primary Education.

318 The results relative to the proportion of correct answers showed, in general (global
319 scores of the three sessions), that the proportion of correct answers was higher in the group of
320 participants with greater spatial ability (↓SA = 0.75 vs. ↑SA = 0.82). In any case, no
321 interaction was obtained between the time of evaluation and the level of spatial ability,
322 suggesting that both groups had a similar performance throughout the three sessions.
323 Moreover, both boys and girls had a comparable performance in the proportion of correct
324 answers throughout the entire training program, thus, no interaction was found between the
325 factors of Session and Gender (boys = 0.77 vs. girls = 0.80). It is interesting to mention that
326 the proportion of correct answers progressively and significantly decreased from the first to
327 the third session, in both groups according to the level of spatial ability, and also in both
328 genders, possibly due to the progressive increase in the level of difficulty of the task in each
329 of the sessions.

330 No significant differences were found in the RTs of both groups according to initial
331 spatial ability (\downarrow SA = 5.1 sec. vs. \uparrow SA = 5.0 sec.), or as a function of gender (boys = 4.8 sec.
332 vs. girls = 5.3 sec.). This result could be in line with those found by Wiedenbauer and Jansen-
333 Osmann (2008), who did not find differences in RT between boys and girls aged 10 and 11
334 years. However, the analyses showed that the girls with better spatial skills were the ones
335 who needed the most time to respond (RTs significantly higher than the rest of the groups).

336 In studies on gender differences in spatial abilities, certain discrepancies have been
337 found. Some studies argue that spatial interventions minimize gender differences (see Linn &
338 Hyde, 1989, for a review), while others find that the gender gap in spatial performance does
339 not narrow (Baenninger & Newcombe, 1989). Our results are congruent with those of studies
340 carried out in schoolchildren where it has been observed that both genders benefit to the same
341 extent after a training program in spatial reasoning (Hawes et al., 2017; Lowrie et al., 2017).
342 Boys have shown similar increases to girls after spatial training, and this finding has also
343 been seen in both groups according to their level of spatial ability.

344

345 **STUDY 2**

346 **Method**

347 *Participants*

348 A total of 21 students ($M = 14.3$ years, $SD = 0.44$; 11 boys and 10 girls) from 3rd year
349 of Secondary Education of the CEU-San Pablo de Montepríncipe School (Boadilla del
350 Monte, Madrid), with a medium-high sociocultural level, took part in this study. These
351 students belonged to the EG of a previous study where the performance between a trained
352 group was compared with an untrained group (Rodán et al., 2016).

353

354 *Materials*

355 *Raven's progressive matrices (SPM version; Raven et al., 1996)*

356 It is the same instrument used and described in Study 1, and its application was carried
357 out with the same procedure.

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359 *EFAI-3 spatial aptitude test "E"*

360 Spatial subtest from the Factorial Assessment of Intellectual Aptitudes battery
361 (Santamaría et al., 2005) similar to that described in the Primary school study. For the study
362 of spatial skills in this group, Level 3 was used, which is recommended for participants

363 between 12 and 15 years of age. This level consists of 27 assessment exercises plus two
364 practice examples (maximum 27 points). The task requires the participant to combine the
365 rotated figure from the answer options with other pieces already placed on the *target* for the
366 puzzle to be completed. The time for this test is six minutes. The studies carried out by
367 Santamaría et al. show reliability indices of .71 (Santamaría et al., 2005).

368

369 *Mental Rotation Training Program (PERM)*

370 This version of PERM consists of 330 double response trials (for a total of 660
371 responses or decisions). Each presentation consists of a white mold on a gray box (reference
372 *target*) located on the left side of the screen, and two two-dimensional figures located on the
373 right side - listed as "1" and "2" - with an identical shape to that of the mold (Figure 3). The
374 difficulty within each session and between sessions increased, manipulating the complexity
375 of the figures, in terms of their symmetry, number of stimuli, discontinuity, etc. The task
376 requires the participant to mentally imagine rotations and indicate whether or not figure "1"
377 on the right fits into the mold, and then repeat the task with figure "2", in such a way that, to
378 access the consecutive trial, the participant must respond to each figure, finally registering a
379 total of 600 responses out of the 660 that are presented in the set of three sessions (the first 10
380 double trials of each session were for familiarization with the task). The correct responses
381 (hits) and response times of each trial were recorded in each session (for additional
382 information on PERM, see Rodán et al., 2016).

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Figure 3. Example of a trial used in PERM in Study 2

394 *Procedure*

395 The tests were administered on five consecutive days, with one session per day,
396 distributed in three well-differentiated phases.

397 The Raven Progressive Matrices and EFAI-3 tests of the pretest phase were
398 administered collectively on the first day, on individual tables in the students' usual
399 classroom, and supervised by three examiners. The order of the tests and the rest between
400 them was the same as in Study 1.

401 The PERM training was applied individually in the computer room during three
402 consecutive sessions, one per day. Ten practice trials were carried out to facilitate the
403 understanding of the task. The training consisted of 100 presentations (200 decisions) in each
404 session. The experimenters' instructions to the participants were the same as in Study 1. The
405 number of trials per session presented in PERM was 4200 (100 trials x 2 decisions x 21
406 participants). After eliminating some trials due to anticipation or excess time consumed, a
407 total of 3730 (88.8%), 3778 (90.0%) and 3672 (87.4%) were finally analyzed in sessions S1,
408 S2 and S3, respectively. After eliminating these trials, the minimum time to perform was 162
409 sec. (2.70 min.), 174 sec. (2.90 min.) and 180 sec. (3.00 min.), while the maximum time was
410 1146 sec. (19.1 min.), 684 sec. (11.4 min.) and 660 sec. (11.0 min.) for S1, S2 and S3,
411 respectively.

412 Finally, on the last day, the Raven Progressive Matrices and EFAI-3 tests were
413 administered under the same conditions as in the pretest phase.

414 All the legal guardians of the participants signed an informed consent, and the study
415 was approved by the Ethics Committee of the UNED.

416

417 *Data Analyses*

418 The analyses performed in this study were identical to those performed in Study 1.

419

420 **Results**

421 *Preliminary Analyses*

422 Both groups (\downarrow SA and \uparrow SA) did not differ in intelligence in the previous phase. No
423 gender differences were found for the whole group, nor for the interaction between Group
424 and Gender factors.

425

426 *Performance during PERM and gains obtained in MR skill*

427 The SA level (\downarrow SA and \uparrow SA) of the EG boys and girls was determined according to the
 428 EFAI-E median in the pretest phase, which in this case was also 9 points. Using the same
 429 criteria as in Study 1, a total of 1420 trials (11.3% of the total) were finally excluded. The
 430 average RT in seconds was calculated for each participant only for the correct answers.

431 Table 3 shows the descriptive analyses of the proportion of correct answers and the RTs
 432 of the correct trials. In relation to the proportion of correct answers in each of the three
 433 sessions (S1, S2, S3) and for the total sessions (TOTAL), the mixed ANOVA 2 (Gender) x 2
 434 (SA level) revealed a main effect of Gender in Session 1 [$F(1, 17) = 5.02, MSE = .058, p =$
 435 $.039, \eta^2_p = .23$], due to a higher proportion of correct answers in girls (girls $M = 0.84$, boys: M
 436 $= 0.73$, mean difference = 0.11, $p = .039$). Also, an effect of the SA level was seen in Session
 437 3 [$F(1, 17) = 12.4, MSE = .12, p = .003, \eta^2_p = .42$], and for the total of all sessions [$F(1, 17) =$
 438 $6.64, MSE = .052, p = .020, \eta^2_p = .28$], so that, in both cases, the group of participants with
 439 high SA obtained a higher proportion of correct answers [CA-S3: \downarrow SA: $M = 0.69$, \uparrow SA: $M =$
 440 0.84 , mean difference = 0.15, $p < .01$; CA-TOTAL: \downarrow SA: $M = 0.72$, \uparrow SA: $M = 0.82$, mean
 441 difference = 0.10, $p = .02$]. The high SA group had a higher proportion of correct answers in
 442 Session 2, but only a marginal effect was found [$F(1, 17) = 3.83, MSE = .032, p = .067, \eta^2_p =$
 443 $.18$]. No other main effects or interactions were found. The repeated measures ANOVA 3
 444 (Session) x 2 (Gender) x 2 (SA level) showed a significant interaction between Session x
 445 Gender factors [$F(2, 34) = 8.22, MSE = .016, p = .001, \eta^2_p = .33$], which was explained by a
 446 decrease in the proportion of correct answers from S1 to S3 in the group of girls [S1: $M =$
 447 0.84 ; S2: $M = 0.77$; S3: $M = 0.77$; mean difference S1-S2 = 0.06, $p < .01$; mean difference
 448 S1-S3 = 0.07, $p = .01$]. A significant interaction between Session x SA level [$F(2, 34) =$
 449 $4.92, MSE = .010, p = .013, \eta^2_p = .22$] was also obtained, so that only the group of
 450 participants with low SA decreased the proportion of correct answers from the first to the last
 451 session [S1: $M = 0.75$; S3: $M = 0.69$; mean difference S1-S3 = 0.05, $p = .04$]. No other effects
 452 or significant interactions were found for this variable. For the RTs, a marginal effect of the
 453 Gender x SA level interaction was found in Session 3 [$F(1, 17) = 4.11, MSE = 4000, p =$
 454 $.059, \eta^2_p = .20$], which was explained by lower RTs in boys in the low SA group and in girls
 455 in the high SA group. No other effects or significant interactions were found. The repeated
 456 measures ANOVA 3 (Session) x 2 (Gender) x 2 (SA level) showed a significant main effect
 457 of the Session factor, due to the fact that the RTs decreased from S1 to S3 [$F(2, 34) = 4.62,$
 458 $MSE = 3176, p = .017, \eta^2_p = .21$]. Pairwise comparisons showed significantly longer RTs in
 459 S1 compared to S3 [S1: $M = 5.2$ seg.; S3: $M = 4.4$ seg.; mean difference S1-S3 = 0.8, $p =$

460 .05]. No other significant interactions were found. Figure 4 shows the performance through
 461 the different training sessions in Secondary students.

462
 463 Table 3
 464 *Descriptive statistics (means and standard deviations) of the proportion of correct answers and RTs of correct trials*
 465 *(in seconds) for each session and for the total of the three sessions of PERM among secondary school students.*
 466

Total (N = 21)				
Measures	↓SA (n = 11)		↑SA (n = 10)	
	Boys (n = 6)	Girls (n = 5)	Boys (n = 5)	Girls (n = 5)
	M (SD)	M (SD)	M (SD)	M (SD)
CA-S1	0.67 (0.11)	0.82 (0.05)	0.78 (0.17)	0.85 (0.06)
CA-S2	0.70 (0.07)	0.75 (0.10)	0.80 (0.13)	0.80 (0.06)
CA-S3	0.66 (0.13)	0.87 (0.07)	0.72 (0.08)	0.81 (0.08)
CA-TOTAL	0.68 (0.10)	0.76 (0.07)	0.82 (0.11)	0.82 (0.06)
RT-S1	4.8 (1.1)	6.1 (1.2)	4.9 (1.2)	4.8 (1.0)
RT-S2	4.2 (1.3)	5.3 (1.1)	4.2 (1.4)	4.8 (1.4)
RT-S3	3.5 (0.7)	5.1 (0.9)	4.6 (1.1)	4.5 (1.3)
RT-TOTAL	4.3 (0.8)	5.5 (0.9)	4.5 (0.8)	4.6 (1.0)

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485 *Figure 4. Proportion of correct answers (A) and response time of correct answers (B) for the interaction*
 486 *Sessions 1 to 3 x Gender x Spatial ability level in Secondary school students*

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488 Table 4 shows the descriptive analyses of the scores obtained in the EFAI-E in both
 489 genders and according to the level of spatial ability. The repeated measures ANOVA 2 (pre-
 490 post) x 2 (gender) x 2 (SA level) for the dependent variable “EFAI-E” showed a main effect
 491 on the time factor [$F(1, 17) = 88.1, MSE = 32, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .84$], which indicates an
 492 improvement, in general, in MR ability. No other significant interactions between factors
 493 were found.

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510 Table 4
 511 *Descriptive statistics (means and standard deviations) of the scores obtained in the EFAI-E in*
 512 *both genders for the group of Secondary school participants with low and high levels of spatial*
 513 *ability.*
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 515

↓SA (n = 11)			
EFAI-E (max. = 30)	Boys (n = 6)	Girls (n = 5)	TOTAL
	M (SD)	M (SD)	M (SD)
Pretest	7.50 (1.05)	7.40 (0.89)	7.45 (0.93)
Post-test	11.5 (2.35)	12.4 (2.30)	11.9 (2.26)
Increment	4.00 (1.67)	5.00 (2.35)	4.45 (1.97)
↑SA (n = 10)			
EFAI-E (max. = 30)	Boys (n = 5)	Girls (n = 5)	TOTAL
	M (SD)	M (SD)	M (SD)
Pretest	12.8 (3.19)	12.2 (1.48)	12.5 (2.37)
Post-test	20.2 (3.03)	18.0 (1.87)	19.1 (2.64)
Increment	7.40 (3.58)	5.80 (3.03)	6.60 (3.24)

526 Discussion

527 In general, a significantly higher proportion of correct answers on PERM was found in
 528 the group of students with better ability in the spatial test “E” of the EFAI-3 compared to the
 529 group with low spatial ability. The individualized analysis of each session only showed
 530 significant differences between these groups in the last session. In addition, a time x SA level
 531 interaction was observed in the proportion of correct answers, so that the participants with
 532 high SA improved their performance from the first to the third session, while those with low
 533 SA decreased throughout the three sessions.

534 A higher proportion of correct answers was also observed in the group of girls for the
 535 total sample of the experimental group. However, the girls only differed significantly from
 536 the boys in the first training session. In addition, a Session x Gender interaction was found, as
 537 the group of girls experienced a significant decrease in the proportion of correct answers from
 538 the first to the last session. Another finding was that boys with high SA increased their
 539 correct answer ratio as the program progressed, although no significant gender differences

540 were observed between high and low spatial ability groups across the different training
541 sessions.

542 Although only the students with poorer spatial ability on the EFAI-3 experienced a
543 significant decrease in RTs from the first to the last session of PERM, both groups with high
544 and low spatial ability had a similar performance throughout training in this variable. No
545 differences were found in the RTs of boys and girls, in line with the findings of Wiedenbauer
546 and Jansen-Osmann (2008), who also did not see a gender effect in response times in an MR
547 task in schoolchildren.

548 Our results in the adolescent population converge with those found in other studies
549 carried out in the same age group, which maintain that both genders benefit in a similar way
550 after a training program in spatial reasoning (Neubauer et al., 2010; Samsudin et al., 2011;
551 Sanz de Acedo Lizarraga & García Ganuza, 2003). Regarding the gains obtained with
552 training, our study is convergent with other studies that did not find differential gains
553 according to the starting level in interventions with 3-year-old preschoolers (Fernández-
554 Méndez et al., 2020) or with university adults (Sims & Mayer, 2002).

555

556 **GENERAL DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS**

557 Any intervention on spatial skills that occurs before or during adolescence could be
558 crucial, especially when the presence of people with fewer spatial resources (including
559 women) is scarce in certain university degrees related to science, technology, engineering and
560 mathematics. Therefore, and according to what was suggested by Uttal et al. (2013) in their
561 influential meta-analysis on malleability of spatial skills, we carried out a study using an
562 analogous method across two different age groups -primary and secondary-, both for the pre-
563 post evaluation, and for MR training, to thus be able to compare the results obtained over
564 three training sessions. The objective of the present two studies was to analyze the
565 performance of the task throughout a training in MR using PERM, examining the
566 performance of the participants by gender and by levels of spatial ability (low and high SA in
567 the spatial aptitude test "E" of EFAI-3). Also, the differential gains produced after training
568 were assessed according to gender and starting spatial level. Based on the previous literature,
569 we expected that participants with lower initial spatial skills would experience greater gains
570 until reaching a similar level after training to those participants with higher spatial resources.

571 In general (global scores of the three sessions), there were only differences in the
572 proportion of correct answers, so that it was lower in participants with low SA. However,

573 students with “low” SA performed well, reaching a ratio of correct answers through the three
574 training sessions of 0.75 and 0.72, in primary and secondary students, respectively. In any
575 case, these results differ significantly from those obtained by participants with high spatial
576 skills (0.82 in trained primary and secondary students).

577 The evolution analyses throughout the three sessions also showed certain points of
578 convergence and divergence between the two age groups. In the group of schoolchildren, the
579 proportion of correct answers declined significantly, and their responses were slower from
580 the first to the last session, although we cannot conclude if these results were due to the
581 increase in the difficulty of the task as the training program progressed or to a lack of
582 motivation. In any case, in general, the level of correct answers in schoolchildren was good
583 (0.83 in Session 1; 0.76 in Session 3). However, in the adolescent group, RTs significantly
584 decreased from the first session (5.2 sec.) to the last (4.4 sec.), keeping their correct answer
585 ratio practically constant throughout the three sessions (≈ 0.77). This could indicate that,
586 despite the increase in the difficulty of the task as sessions progressed, their level of
587 motivation and/or their learning allowed them to respond faster and maintain an optimal level
588 of correct answers.

589 The correct answer ratio profiles did show differences in both age groups, only finding
590 variations across the three sessions by gender groups and SA in adolescents. By gender
591 groups, the boys improved their MR ability from the first session to the last, while the girls
592 worsened from the beginning to the end of the training program. These results could be
593 explained because the boys were more motivated to produce correct answers throughout the
594 different PERM sessions, similar to the results found by Voyer et al. (2004), who suggested
595 that men seem to be more motivated by the need to produce answers, showing less response
596 guessing behavior.

597 An aspect that is scarcely valued in the literature on MR training using an analogous
598 method at different ages is that of the increases produced as a function of the initial spatial
599 level. In the present work, similar results have been found among both age groups, so that
600 participants with low spatial ability benefited in a similar proportion to those participants
601 with better spatial abilities. These findings are compatible with the results of studies on
602 gender differences in spatial skills, in which it has been observed that both genders benefit to
603 the same extent after training in spatial reasoning, both in primary schoolchildren (Hawes et
604 al., 2017; Lowrie et al., 2017) and in secondary school adolescents (Neubauer et al., 2010;
605 Samsudin et al., 2011; Sanz de Acedo Lizarraga & García Ganuza, 2003). Our results also

606 converge with those obtained in studies that have not found differential gains after spatial
607 training according to the starting level in MR in 3-year-old preschoolers (Fernández-Méndez
608 et al., 2020) and university adults (Sims & Mayer, 2002).

609 Finally, it is worth mentioning the variability in the time spent on the training task in
610 both studies, which shows that some participants need a substantially longer time to achieve
611 optimal performance. This is important for the design of adaptive training programs, so that,
612 to access a higher level of difficulty, a minimum should be reached that ensures that the most
613 basic items have been assimilated. Only in this way could this type of training be more
614 effective and have an educational purpose, especially in those participants who have fewer
615 resources.

616

617 **Limitations of the study and future lines of research**

618 The small number of participants in both studies, especially in secondary school (N =
619 21), could have affected the analyses of variance, thus caution must be taken in generalizing
620 the conclusions obtained. In this sense, it would be desirable for future research to have a
621 larger sample to ensure the generalization of results.

622 In our opinion, the training program is not lacking in intensity (450 and 600 trials in
623 schoolchildren and adolescents, respectively), and, in general, the participants showed a high
624 level of motivation and competitiveness with their peers to perform at their best. However,
625 three sessions may have been insufficient to show greater increases in individuals with low
626 spatial ability. In this sense, Terlecki et al. (2008) followed twelve weeks of spatial training,
627 finding that participants with lower spatial abilities needed some time to show spatial gains
628 and catch up with participants with better abilities. In future studies, the analysis of the
629 relationship between the total time it takes to perform the task (including trials that are not
630 correct) and the proportion of correct answers, as well as the analysis of the progression
631 throughout the trials, would allow further knowledge regarding the profile of evolution in a
632 student's learning, as a function of total time, when this type of training is carried out.

633 Despite these limitations, we believe that the present work is of interest to establish
634 guidelines in the design of programs to improve spatial cognition, promoting and
635 implementing adaptive and personalized training to help students with more deficits.

636 In the two studies in this work, an MR training task has been used that falls within the
637 intrinsic-dynamic category (see Uttal et al., 2013) and that involves manipulation or
638 transformation in an egocentric frame of reference. However, the field of spatial skills could

639 imply the use of very different contexts, such as extrinsic-dynamic ones, and even of an
 640 allocentric type, where the frame of reference regarding the stimulus that is rotated is
 641 external. This type of spatial scenario is frequently used by drone pilots or air traffic
 642 controllers. In this sense, it would be interesting to assess to what extent a training with this
 643 type of mental transformation tasks can influence the acquisition of strategies to optimally
 644 carry out problems related to STEM domains, where to reach a solution the use of this type of
 645 mental representations could be needed.

646

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